

Veli Pasha Complex of Ioannina

also known as “Veli Pasha Mosque of Ioannina”, “Çukur Cami of Ioannina”

By Theodoros Tzanatos, University of Vienna

Entry tags: Religious Group, Religious Place, Abrahamic, Religious Complex, Greece, Mosque, Islam, Epirus, Language, Turkic, Greek, Turkish, Arabic, Ottoman Turkish, Sunnism, Balkan Traditions

The Veli Pasha Complex, built by Ali Tepedelenli Pasha's son, Veli Pasha, was originally consisted of a mosque, a kitchen, and a medrese (Islamic school). According to one view, it was erected on the site of an earlier structure, the Mosque of Bali Kethuda. While the mosque underwent restoration in the late 1970s, it remains closed to the public. However, consolidation work was undertaken on the medrese in 1983. From that point on, the building had various uses, mainly by the municipality of the city.

Date Range: 1788 CE - 1913 CE

Region: Litharitsia, Ioannina

Region tags: Europe, Greece, Balkans, Epirus

Litharitsia hill of Ioannina

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

- An empire

Notes: At the time of its construction. Nowadays, of course a state.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

- Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Allah

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Men

– Other [specify]: Local Elite

Notes: The complex was built by the son of the Ottoman regional magnate, Ali Tepedelenli Pasha.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Private individual

Notes: Provincial magnates of the Ottoman Empire, i.e., the family of Ali Tependelenli Pasha.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: I do not know.

Notes: It is evident that the complex was built in order to provide social outreach to the local community, especially the Muslims. While the Medrese provided education, the kitchen was used to arrange food to the poor and the mosque for religious facilities like the prayers. It is unknown if Veli Pasha had a certain intention for founding his complex apart from the aforementioned aspects.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: Hill

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Clearing

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Fotopoulos, Kostas. Τα Γιάννινα. Οι Μαχαλάδες Τα Σοκάκια Και Τα Τοπωνύμιά Τους Με Τις Ιστορικές Και Λαογραφικές Παραδόσεις Και Ανέκδοτα. Athens: Βιβλιοθήκη Ηπειρωτικής Εταιρείας Αθηνών, 1986.

– Source 2: Demetracopoulou, Polixeni. "Veli Pasha Complex" in Ottoman Architecture in Greece. Edited by Ersi Brouskari. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Has this place been looted:

– I don't know

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 Description: The Odysseus database of the Greek Ministry of Culture and Sports

– Source 2 URL: <https://kulturenvanteri.com/en/yer/veli-pasa-camii-yanya/#17.1/39.6645/20.85528>

– Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=18942

– Source 2 Description: Cultural database

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: 1978-1979 and 1983 for the mosque and the medrese, 1995-1997 for the kitchen.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The minaret of the mosque, along with the vast majority of the minarets found in the city of Ioannina, after the entrance of the Greek army in the city in 1913.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: Partially in the 1980s.

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Notes: Not once (compulsory option).

↳ In modernity

– Other (date-range):: 1980-2000

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Political

Notes: And worship and social.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: slate roof, ashlar rocks etc.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 60

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Grass

– I don't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Lime

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Glass

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– I don't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: External masonry

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– I don't know

Notes: The monuments are altered or closed

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– I don't know

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No other

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– I don't know

Notes: The monuments are altered or closed

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– I don't know

Notes: The monuments are altered or closed

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human,

anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– I don't know

Notes: The monuments are altered or closed

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– I don't know

Notes: The monuments are altered or closed

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god present:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Do they have another type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Do they have kin relation with elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ other:

–Other [specify]: no other

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer.

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: I do not know.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Notes: Historically yes, when there was a muslim community in the city and it was a part of the Ottoman Empire. There was a muslim community in Epirus until 1923 and the Population Exchange between Greece and Turkey.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: Historically providing food, education and religious functions to the community. Currently, parts of the complex are used by the Municipality of Ioannina for various uses.

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Not currently but in the past, prior to 1913.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: Not currently but in the past, prior to 1913.

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Veli Pasha Complex of Ioannina, Demetracopoulou, Polixeni. Ottoman Architecture in Greece. Edited by Ersi Brouskari. Athens: Hellenic Ministry of Culture, 2008. p.174-175

Reference: Veli Pasha Complex of Ioannina, Fotopoulos, Kostas. Τα Γιάννινα. Οι Μαχαλάδες Τα Σοκάκια Και Τα Τοπωνύμιά Τους Με Τις Ιστορικές Και Λαογραφικές Παραδόσεις Και Ανέκδοτα. Athens: Βιβλιοθήκη Ηπειρωτικής Εταιρείας Αθηνών, 1986.

Reference: Veli Pasha Complex of Ioannina, Gara, Eleni, and Georgios Tzedopoulos. Χριστιανοί Και Μουσουλμάνοι Στην Οθωμανική Αυτοκρατορία. Athens: Kallipos Repository, 2015.

Reference: Veli Pasha Complex of Ioannina, Kolovos, Elias. Στους Καιρούς Των Σουλτάνων. Athens: Asini, 2023.

Reference: Veli Pasha Complex of Ioannina, Kolovos, Elias, Giorgos Pallis, and Panagiotis Poulos, eds.. Οθωμανικά Μνημεία Στην Ελλάδα. Κληρονομίες Υπό Διαπραγμάτευση. Edited by Elias Kolovos, Giorgos Pallis, and Panagiotis Poulos. Athens: Kapon, 2023.